

Offshore Jacket Platform Leg Response to Vessel Impact

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Abstract: A response analysis has shown significantly low deformation and non-linear characteristics of force-deformation curves of the jacket leg, but a more rigorous approach is required in the calculation and analysis. Therefore, Johnson-Cook Constitutive Model has been used for the response analyses for different scenarios of stresses and deformation studies in this paper. To access the effect of the jacket braces on the ConocoPhillips Belanak Wellhead jacket leg deformation, this study and analysis have considered a service vessel colliding at a point on a joint and also away from the joint on the jacket leg during the worst expected weather condition on the Natuna sea for sideways, head-on and manoeuvring collisions.

Keywords: Constitutive Model, Johnson-Cook Model, Response Analysis, Stresses, Deformation, Collision

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Introduction

Ship-platform collision is undoubtedly one of the major causes of large deformations that leads to structural damage. Kenny, in 1998, reported three collision incidents between large vessels such as semi-submersible work barges, drilling rigs and jackets under construction^[1]. Also, Supply vessels, passing merchants' vessels, and shuttle tankers according to Flatoy (2018) are major threats to offshore structures and Jackets^[2]. Being a dynamic phenomenon, ship-platform collisions have negative impacts on the environment, materials, and economy and may produce deadly consequences on the lives of humans. Due to the above reasons, at the design stage of the jacket platform, the dynamic collision response ought to be analyzed to ensure that, the jacket platform has enough strength to withstand collisions. That precaution will ensure that there is a lower probability of severe collision damage^[3].

Generally, ship-platform collisions cannot be prevented due to crew unconsciousness or errors, technology and unforeseen harsh environmental conditions but could be managed. One way to reduce the risk of ship impacts is to set up a safety zone around the platform, while another alternative is radar monitoring. However, this will not protect the platforms against driven collisions, where the ship hits a platform at full speed^[4].

Finally, the interaction of member denting and member bending are the main factors influencing the resistance of jacket platforms to ship collisions and that could be designed to minimize damage during collision incidence. Hence, there is

a need to study the dynamic impact buckling of the legs of jacket platforms. The conclusions drawn will help in the jacket platform structural design process by engineers as well as stakeholders' policy formulation.

ConocoPhillips Belanak Wellhead Platform

In 2014, Sumiwi and Afrizal studied and analyzed the ConocoPhillips Belanak Wellhead Platform of the Natuna Sea leg local and global deformation using ANSYS LS-DYNA for the local deformation studies and GT-STRUDL 27.0 version for the global analysis. To design structural members to minimize the damage of impact, a much more robust improvement is to be done to further study the deformation and stresses of the structure to help the decision makers on the formulation of safety zones around the platform and also to help Designers on the choice of platform leg thickness for platforms to be built in the Natuna sea in the future since collisions at sea can only be managed and not prevented. The Conoco Wellhead Platform is no exception to jacket platforms that have suffered collisions with service vessels, therefore, there was a need to study these deformations to make informed decisions.

This paper discusses the stresses and deformation on the leg of the ConocoPhillips Belanak Wellhead Platform Leg at the Natuna Sea. The Platform is a jacket type, offshore and fixed in the bed of the shallow waters of the Natuna sea, for drilling crude oil. Details of the platform are provided in Tables 1 and 2. The uniqueness of this research is that, as already indicated, it does not only consider a random impact point on the platform leg as studied by Sumiwi and Afrizal but rather, a point on the joint where the bracings are attached, that is, 65m (shall be known as on-joint impact point in this research) from the seabed and point away from these joint, that is 65.69m (it shall be known as off-joint impact point in this research) to provide a better understanding of the dent depth and stresses generated in the three collision scenarios. The jacket was analyzed using two powerful software ANSYS and LS-DYNA running different scenarios for impact velocity, water level, side of impact and impact position. The vessel mass and platform size remained unchanged^[5].

Table 1: Jacket Platform and Vessel Dimensions

Items	Dimensions
Jacket Bottom	70.0m × 65.2m
Jacket Top	31.0m×24.5m × 2.9m
Deck	53.1m×47.2m×2.9m
Deck Thickness	2.900m
Vertical Height	90.000m
Total Vertical Height	92.900m
Air Gab	18.000m
Length of Leg	92.472m
Leg radius (inner)	1.465m
Leg radius (outer)	1.681m
Leg thickness	0.216m
Bracings' thickness	0.500m

Table 2: Deck and Bracings Dimensions Elevations

Members	Length (m)	number	Interval (m)	Height Ref: bed	Elevation(m) Ref: sea surface
Top of Deck	-	-	2.900	92.900	+15.400
First Horizontal Bracings	40.000	2			
	37.257	2	25.000	90.00	+12.500
Impact position or water level	-	-	12.500	77.500	0.000
Second Horizontal Bracings	48.333	2			
	45.019	2	30.000	65.000	-12.500
Third Horizontal Bracings	58.348	2			
	54.347	2	35.000	35.000	-42.500
Fourth Horizontal Bracings	70.000	2			
	65.200	2	0.000	0.000	-77.500
First Set of Diagonal Bracings	50.926	4			
	47.434	4	-	-	-
Second Set of Diagonal Bracings	61.400	4			
	57.190	4	-	-	-
Third Set of Diagonal Bracings.	73.338	4			
			-	-	-

Johnson-Cook(J-C) Material Characterization

Constitutive modelling is the mathematical description of how materials respond to various loadings. This is the most intensely researched field within solid mechanics because of its complexity and the importance of accurate constitutive models for practical engineering problems. In 1985, Johnson and Cook proposed a constitutive model, that can describe the material under dynamic loading. The dynamic mechanical behaviour of the material under the impact, especially the material's mechanical response in the penetration process, such as shear loading, can be described by the Johnson-Cook constitutive model according to research^[6].

The Johnson-Cook constitutive model used in this work reflects the effect of strain hardening as well as the strain hardening rate. The corresponding stress-plastic strain can be expressed in EQ.1 to reflect the material properties and more accurately, the ductile fracture behaviour of steel under a shear loading situation. This type of constitutive model was chosen for this research because, it solves the problem at hand to a satisfactory extent, which includes the consideration of the strain rate which is a major factor influencing the energy dissipation involves in the collision mechanism as already indicated. Finally, according to Storheim (2015), the proposed constitutive model can describe the ductile fracture process of steel better and predicts the structural response more accurately in various scenarios of ship collisions in numerical simulation^[7]. The J-C constitutive model is a multiplicative law and also a strain, temperature-dependent viscoplastic model suited for high strain rate process as expressed in EQ.1

$$\sigma_{eq} = (A + B (\epsilon_p)^n) (1 + C \ln(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\dot{\epsilon}_r})) (1 - T^{*m}) \tag{EQ.1}$$

where A, B, C n, m are Strength constants, model coefficients, or material constants. These are the five parameters that require calibration. The first term in the Johnson-Cook constitutive equation corresponds to the quasi-static material properties of dimensionless temperature $T^* = 0$ or since this modelling analyzes results under constant temperature, m, T_{melt} and T_0 were not considered) and reference strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_r$, equal to $0.1 \cdot 10^{-5} s^{-1}$, therefore, the constitutive model, becomes the following in EQ.2

$$\sigma_{eq}=(A+B(\epsilon^p)) \tag{EQ.2}$$

The second term $(1+C \ln(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\dot{\epsilon}_r}))$ and the third term $(1- T^{*m})$ in the Johnson-Cook constitutive equation correspond to the strain rate and the temperature sensitivity of the material respectively. Due to the high strain and high strain rate, the thermal softening of the material will affect the equivalent stress as shown in the Equivalent plastic strain EQ.3

$$\epsilon^f = [D_1 + D_2 e^{(\sigma^* D_3)}][1 + D_4 \ln \epsilon^*] [1 + D_5 T^*] \tag{EQ.3}$$

Where σ^* is the ratio of the average of the three normal stresses to the assumed von Mises equivalent stress ($\sigma^* \leq 1.5$), T and m characterize the thermal softening of the material. Damage or Material parameters (D_1, D_2, D_3, D_4, D_5) are -0.8, 2.1, -0.5, 0.002 and 0.61 respectively. They are also called fracture or damage constants and are usually calibrated. $A, B,$ and n characterize the strain hardening ϵ_0 and C characterize strain rate hardening or dimensionless strain rate, T_{room}, T_{melt} and m characterize temperature softening, and T is the instantaneous temperature. ANSYS made provision for the input of J-C failure parameters. With known values of J-C failure parameters of steel S355 from the literature, The Equivalent failure strain during the impact was solved in ANSYS.

Research Methodology

Jacket Modification

The platform as modelled in GT-Strudl 27.0 version by Sumiwi and Afrizal in 2014 is shown in Fig.1 whilst the same structure has been modelled in this paper with ANSYS 17.2 version as indicated in Fig.2. The simplification of the structure in this paper resulted from removing all the unwanted structural parts that play no role in the collision process. They are zero-force members. Again, the members that were not directly involved in the collision process yet were carrying loads were converted into imposed loads onto the structure accordingly during the modelling process. For instance, the double-decked platform in Fig.1 has been converted into a pressure load in Fig.2. The total weight and size of the structure remained unchanged after the modification. Again, the motive behind that was to pay much attention to the bracing effect in the collision process as much as possible and to achieve that, the structure needed simplification. Finally, overcoming the problem of overlapping nodes leading to errors in model verification was achieved in a simplified structure with the ANSYS as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.1: 3D Modelling in GT-Strudl 27.0 version^[5]

Fig.2: 3D Modelling in ANSYS 17.2 version

Engineering Data

The vessels and the fixed Jacket Platform material properties have been listed in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively. The type of material and its properties were input under the engineering data section of ANSYS.

The Fixed Jacket Platform: Steel 355

Table 3: Engineering Data in ANSYS

Property	Value	Unit
Density	7.896E-09	tonne mm ⁻³
Isotropic Elasticity		
Young's Modulus	2.1E+05	MPa
Poisson ratio	0.3	
Bulk Modulus	1.75E+05	MPa
Shear Modulus	80769	MPa
Specific Heat	4.52E+08	MJ tonne ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Johnson Cook Strength		
Strain Rate Correction	First-Order	
Initial Yield Stress	450	MPa
Hardening Constant	300	MPa
Hardening Exponent	0.3	
Strain Rate Constant	0.0326	
Thermal Softening Exponent	1	
Melting Temperature	1400	C
Reference Strain Rate(/sec)	1	
Shear Modulus	80769	MPa
Johnson Cook failure		
Damage Constants		
D1	0.150	
D2	2.000	
D3	-1.500	
D4	0.002	
D5	0.61	

The Impacting Vessel

The impacting vessel properties have been provided in Table 4

Table 4: The striking vessel material properties

Property	Value	Unit
Density	7.850E-09	tonne mm ⁻³
Isotropic Elasticity		
Young's Modulus	200000	MPa
Poisson ratio	0.3	
Bulk Modulus	1.6667E+05	MPa
Shear Modulus	76923	MPa
Specific Heat	4.34E+08	MJ tonne ⁻¹ C ⁻¹

Geometry

The geometry of the vessel and jacket platform was imported from AUTOCAD 3D (.iges file) onto ANSYS Geometry, as indicated in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig.3: AUTOCAD 3D Model

Fig.4: Ansys Workbench Geometry

Model and Setup

Parameters needed for the simulation of the model were added to the model under the 'model and set up' stage in ANSYS. The solution of the model was obtained at this stage and error warnings were also identified and resolved until model success was achieved. Fig.5 shows the model setup in ANSYS.

Fig.5: Model Setup in ANSYS 17.2 version

In Table 5 are the parameters and inputs with their corresponding units that were input into the ANSYS software for the simulation

Table 5: Parameters and Inputs

Parameters	Input	Unit
Body Interactions	Frictional	
Friction coefficient	0.15	
Dynamic Coefficient	0.1	
Meshing type	Varied	mm
	Body sizing for the platform (0.008)	
Velocity(m/s)	varied	m/s
End Time	0.002	s
Maximum Energy Error (%)	0	
Applied Vertical Load	varied	tonne
Support conditions for the platform	Fixed	
Output Controls	200	

Boundary Condition

[1] The jacket

The jacket was modelled with soil layers which shall represent the seabed. No modifications were made to these layers. The jacket was restricted to only vertical motions. (Thus, restrained against oscillation and rotation along the horizontal axes). According to Watan (2011), a fixed column for impact assessments was legit because flexibility at the ends contributed no or relatively little influence on the outcome of the deformation process^[8].

[2] The striking service vessel

The bow

The nodes on the other sides were restricted to keep the bow moving along the direction of impact. Besides, all the nodes in the bow model are given an initial velocity the same as that of the vessel to avoid deformation lag and shear in the bow model. The bow was designed as a rigid body so, the initial velocity does not die off quickly and the deformation of the vessel is negligible under this study.

The side

The vessel was also not allowed to move in these directions; thus, the vessel was restricted.

The stern

The stern collision was not modelled, as it was assumed to exhibit the same impact behaviour as the bow.

Running the Model

After a successful solution, the LSDYNAexport.k file was obtained from the ANSYS repository and ran in ANSYS MECHANICAL. After the successful run, the output files were imported into LS-DYNA. The stresses and deformation of the structure were viewed and analyzed.

Model Verification

The most important verification was to check that there were no duplicate nodes. When parts were created separately, it was important to verify that, the parts were connected. For example: if two plates or more members were supposed to be connected at one edge but were created separately, both plates or elements will have nodes at the common edge.

The nodes need to be merged to connect those members. Finally, data, research outcomes and conclusions from Sumiwi and Afrizal’s analysis, served as a good source for the model verification.

Collision scenarios

It is very important to predict the impact velocity as accurately as possible since the square of that velocity is equivalent to the impact energy. It is uneconomical to design the jacket platform against the full or maximum speed of the vessels likely to collide with, even though no one can discard the fact that such an extreme case could happen. For this reason, more attention was placed on the collision velocities of attendant vessels (service vessels), which is more likely to happen and can be designed against. The combination of collision velocities for each collision scenario is provided in Table 6.

Table 6: Collision velocities for each scenario

Collision Scenario	MSL		LWL		HWL	
	Regular Velocity (m/s)	Intense Velocity (m/s)	Regular Velocity (m/s)	Intense Velocity (m/s)	Intense Velocity (m/s)	Intense Velocity (m/s)
Stern/Bow	0.38	0.72	0.38	0.72	0.38	0.72
Side	0.27	0.53	0.27	0.53	0.27	0.53
Manoeuvring	0.73	1.28	0.73	1.28	0.73	1.28

Based on the scenario above, the ANSYS LS-DYNA model was produced as shown in Figs. 7,8,9,10,11 and 12.

Fig.6: Meshing

Fig.7: Vertical Loading

Fig.8: Velocity of vessel

Fig.9: Fixed support

Fig.10: 3D modelling in ANSYS LS-DYNA 2.0 version

Fig.11: Off-Joint collision modelling

Fig.12: On-Joint Collision modelling

Simulation Result and Discussion

The Jacket Leg Damage by attendant (Service) Vessel Collision

According to the simulation results obtained from the ANSYS LS-DYNA software, the contact stiffness for regular and extreme cases is shown in Tables 7,8,9 and 10. In all, three collision scenarios have been modelled using numerical simulations. These three were chosen because they cover all the possible impact scenarios that periodically occur on the Natuna Sea. The analysis covered both regular or normal and abnormal operations or conditions at sea, all the time, hence, the results cover a wide range of data as much as possible. The 2500 tonnes service vessel has been chosen for all cases under on-joint and off-joint analysis because the service vessel is widely used on the Natuna sea and is also periodically involved in collisions with jacket platforms on the Natuna sea.

According to the results for the normal(regular) and intensive collisions as indicated in Tables 7,8,9 and 10. Considering Tables 7,8,9,10 for off-joint and on-joint impact, the vessel performing manoeuvring collision had the largest velocity (It is the largest design velocity the vessel is expected to attain in its design life) of 0.73m/s and 1.28m/s for both regular and intense conditions respectively, followed by head-on by 0.27m/s and 0.72m/s for regular and intense conditions, then finally the sideways impact with velocities of 0.38m/s and 0.58m/s also for regular and intense respectively.

The largest kinetic energy was with the manoeuvring drift due to the largest velocity associated with the impact and recorded off-joint values of 9375.913kJ;11030.694kJ at off-joint impact as shown in Tables 7 and 8 respectively and 7721.132kJ; 8603.446kJ for both regular and intense conditions at on-joint impact for both normal and intense conditions

as shown on Tables 9 and 10. The kinetic energy before impact is directly proportional to the square of the velocity of the vessel during manoeuvring.

The side had the least kinetic energy of 1320.931kJ; 1554.077kJ as shown in Tables 7 and 8 for off-joint impact and 1600.811kJ; 1600.811kJ for on-joint impact for both regular and intense analysis due to the large added mass, that the vessel needs to overcome as it moves in that direction. The kinetic energy before impact is equivalent to the deformation energy after the impact on the account that, much of the energy was absorbed during the impact hence the largest deformation of 0.2646m; 0.3113m at off-joint impact as shown in Tables 9 and 10 and 0.2179m;0.2428m at on-joint impact for regular and intense conditions were recorded during the manoeuvring impact.

The intermediary deformation occurred during the head-on impact and the values recorded were 0.2230m; 0.2623m for off-joint impact as shown in Tables 7 and 8 and 0.1836m;0.2046m in Tables 9 and 10 at on-joint impact for regular and intensive conditions respectively.

The sideways impact recorded the least deformation due to the least kinetic energy value. The deformation values were 0.1915m;0.2253m at off-joint as shown in Tables 7 and 8 and 0.1577m; 0.1757m at on-joint as shown in Tables 9 and 10 for regular and intense conditions respectively.

Impact force is directly proportional to the contact stiffness and the impact stress; hence the manoeuvring impact produced the maximum stress of $2.95E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$; $3.05E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$ at off-joint impact and the corresponding stiffnesses in both cases were $0.91E+06 \text{ kN/m}$; $1.07E+06 \text{ kN/m}$ as shown on Tables 7 and 8 and $2.14E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$; $2.38E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$ at on-joint impact as shown on and the corresponding stiffness in both cases were $1.30E+06 \text{ kN/m}$ $1.17E+06 \text{ kN/m}$ for both regular and intense conditions as shown in Tables 9 and 10.

The bow had the higher stress of $2.40E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$; $2.81E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$ at off-joint impact as shown in Tables 7 and 8 and $1.97E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$; $2.19E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$ as shown in Tables 9 and 10. The corresponding stiffnesses were $8.72E+05 \text{ kN/m}$; $7.41E+05 \text{ kN/m}$ as shown in Tables 7 and 8 and $10.59E+05$; $9.50E+05 \text{ kN/m}$ as shown in Tables 9 and 10 for both regular and intense conditions.

Finally, the least stress state was encountered during the sideways collision. Their values were $1.84E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$; $2.16E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$ and had stiffnesses of $9.12E+05 \text{ kN/m}$; $7.75E+05 \text{ kN/m}$ for off-joint impact as shown in Tables 7 and 8 and $1.51E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$; $1.68E+05 \text{ kN/m}^2$ and had stiffness of $7.75E+05 \text{ kN/m}$; $11.07E+05 \text{ kN/m}$ at on-joint impact as shown in Tables 9 and 10 respectively for both normal and intensive conditions which were higher than the stern collision for both regular and intense scenarios of impact.

Table 11 shows the difference between on-joint and off-joint impacts at normal conditions and the difference between the on-joint and off-joint impacts at intensive conditions is indicated in Table 12. The relevance of these data is that the percentage change of deformation and stress between the impact points could be computed to determine the role of braces in the impact (by how much the deformation decreases at points with bracings support) as indicated in Tables 13 and 14. According to Tables 13 and 14, Maneuvering collision recorded the highest deformation; stress difference of 0.0467 m ; 46000 kN/m^2 and 0.0685 m ; $6.70E+04 \text{ kN/m}^2$ between on-joint and off-joint impact for both normal and intensive conditions due to the large change in kinetic energy explained earlier. The stern had the intermediary deformation; stress difference of 0.0394 m ; 43000 kN/m^2 and 0.0577 m ; $6.20E+04 \text{ kN/m}^2$ whilst the least difference of 0.0338 m ; 33000 kN/m^2 and 0.0496 m ; $3.3E+04 \text{ kN/m}^2$ was recorded by the side due to the added mass from water and least incurred impact velocity. Finally, Tables 13 and 14 confirm the correlation that the percentage change in deformation and stress for one scenario of impact, thus, head-on impact between the on-joint and off-joint impact for normal and extreme conditions to be 21.429% and 28.2015% respectively. Hence, it could be concluded that the bracing could reduce the impact of formation or buckling by 21.429%.

Table 7: Contact Stiffness of ANSYS result (regular condition: Point away from joint)

Collision type	Mass of vessel (tonnes)	Velocity Of Vessel (m/s)	Kinetic Energy (kJ)	Dent Depth (m)	Stress Impact (kJ/m ²)	Stiffness (kJ/m)
Stern/Bow	2500	0.27	2025.638	0.2230	2.40E+05	8.72E+05
Sideway	2500	0.38	1320.931	0.1915	1.84E+05	9.12E+05
Manoeuvring	2500	0.73	9375.913	0.2646	2.60E+05	0.91E+06

Table 8: Contact Stiffness of ANSYS result (intense condition: Point away from joint)

Collision type	Mass of vessel (tonnes)	Velocity Of Vessel (m/s)	Kinetic Energy (kJ)	Dent Depth (m)	Stress Impact (kJ/m ²)	Stiffness (kJ/m)
Stern/Bow	2500	0.72	2382.623	0.2623	2.81E+05	7.41E+05
Sideway	2500	0.53	1554.077	0.2253	2.16E+05	7.75E+05
Manoeuvring	2500	1.28	11030.694	0.3113	3.05E+05	1.07E+06

Table 9: Contact Stiffness of ANSYS result (regular condition: Joint Impact)

Collision type	Mass of vessel (tonnes)	Velocity Of Vessel (m/s)	Kinetic Energy (kJ)	Dent Depth (m)	Stress Impact (KN/m ²)	Stiffness (KN/m)
Stern/Bow	2500	0.270	1667.745	0.1836	1.97E+05	10.59E+05
Sideway	2500	0.380	1600.811	0.1577	1.51E+05	11.07E+05
Manoeuvring	2500	0.730	7721.132	0.2179	2.14E+05	1.30E+06

Table 10: Contact Stiffness of ANSYS result (intense condition: Joint Impact)

Collision type	Mass of vessel (tonnes)	Velocity Of Vessel (m/s)	Kinetic Energy (KJ)	Dent Depth (m)	Stress Impact (KN/m ²)	Stiffness (KN/m)
Stern/Bow	2500	0.72	1858.500	0.2046	2.19E+05	9.50E+05
Sideway	2500	0.53	1783.529	0.1757	1.68E+05	9.94E+05
Manoeuvring	2500	1.28	8603.446	0.2428	2.38E+05	1.17E+06

Table 11: The difference: Point away from joint vrs point on the joint (regular condition)

Collision type	Mass of vessel (tonnes)	Velocity Of Vessel (m/s)	Kinetic Energy (kJ)	Dent Depth (m)	Stress Impact (KN/m ²)	Stiffness (KN/m)
Stern/Bow	2500	0.27	357.893	0.0394	43000	-1.87E+05
Sideway	2500	0.38	-279.88	0.0338	33000	-1.95E+05
Manoeuvring	2500	0.73	1654.781	0.0467	46000	-2.30E+05

Table 12: The difference: Point away from joint vrs point on joint (intense condition)

Collision type	Mass of vessel (tonnes)	Velocity Of Vessel (m/s)	Kinetic Energy (KJ)	Dent Depth (m)	Stress Impact KN/m ²	Stiffness KN/m
Stern/Bow	2500	0.72	524.123	0.0577	6.20E+04	-2.09E+05
Sideway	2500	0.53	-229.452	0.0496	3.30E+04	-2.19E+05
Manoeuvring	2500	1.28	2427.248	0.0685	6.70E+04	-2.60E+05

Table 13: Percentage change of deformation (On-joint vrs Off-joint)

Time(s)	Ref. N	Ref. E	On. N	On. E	Off. N	Off. E	%(On-Off)N	%(On-Off)Ex
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-
0.06	0.205	0.257	0.163	0.181	0.197	0.232	21.429	28.205
0.12	0.225	0.277	0.184	0.205	0.223	0.262	21.429	28.205
0.18	0.225	0.277	0.184	0.205	0.223	0.262	21.429	28.205
0.24	0.225	0.277	0.184	0.205	0.223	0.262	21.429	28.205
0.3	0.225	0.277	0.184	0.205	0.223	0.262	21.429	28.205
0.36	0.225	0.277	0.184	0.205	0.223	0.262	21.429	28.205
0.42	0.225	0.277	0.184	0.205	0.223	0.262	21.429	28.205
0.48	0.225	0.277	0.184	0.205	0.223	0.262	21.429	28.205

Table 14: Percentage change of Stress (On-joint vrs Off-joint)

Time(s)	Ref. N	Ref. E	On. N	On. E	Off. N	Off. E	%(On-Off)N	%(On-Off)Ex
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-
0.03	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-
0.045	870	1500	700	780	850	1000	21.42857	28.20513
0.06	53000	65000	42000	46800	51000	60000	21.42857	28.20513
0.09	23599	30000	17500	19500	21250	25000	21.42857	28.20513
0.11	190000	293000	140000	156000	170000	200000	21.42857	28.20513
0.12	196000	294000	196700	219180	238850	281000	21.42857	28.20513
0.18	22000	25000	14000	15600	17000	20000	21.42857	28.20513
0.24	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-
0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-
0.36	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-
0.42	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-
0.48	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-

According to Tables 13 and 14, Ref.N is a Reference value for Normal conditions, Ref.E is the reference value for Extreme Conditions, and On.N and On.E is On-Joint Normal and Extreme values respectively, %(On-Off)N refers to the Percentage change between the On-Joint and Off-joint at normal conditions and, %(On-Off)Ex refers to the Percentage change between the On-Joint and Off-joint at extreme conditions.

Figs. 13,14 and 15 show that the fracture occurred during the impact process with the Bow impact scenario at off-joint impact. The average on-joint and off-joint impact deformations were 0.1941m which is 10.139% lesser than the leg thickness and 0.24265m which is 12.338% more than the leg thickness respectively. The average on-joint and off-joint impacts for sideways impact were 0.1667m which is also 22.824% lesser than the leg thickness and 0.2084m also 3.519%

lesser than the thickness of the jacket leg respectively indicating that no fracture occurred. Also, with an average on-joint and off-joint deformation of 0.2304m equivalent to 6.667% more than the thickness of the leg and 0.2880m, which is 33.333% more than the leg thickness, the manoeuvring collision had fracture occurring in both locations of impact. In summary, from Table 15 the average deformation could be computed as 0.28335m which exceeds the installed jacket leg thickness of 0.216m by 31.181% but falls below the minimum required leg thickness of 0.3362m required to prevent fracture by 23.394%.The general provision for the elements of a jacket structure demands that, if the diagonal bracing, horizontal bracing, and columns had a large dent depth over 10% of the length of the outer diameter of the leg, then, the element must be repaired or replaced^[5]. As shown in Table 15, although, the average dent depth of 0.28335m does not exceed 0.3362, the structure leg needs to be replaced by a minimum leg thickness of 0.288m to avoid fracture.

Table 15:Checking for the structural integrity of the Platform Leg after the collision

Impact scenario	Average On-Joint Deformation (m)	Average off-joint Deformation (m)	Leg outer diameter (m)	10% of Leg outer diameter (m)	Leg Thickness	Minimum leg thickness required(m)	Fracture
Bows	0.1941	0.2427	3.362	0.3362	0.216	0.288	off-joint impact
Side	0.1667	0.2084	3.362	0.3362	0.216	0.288	No Fracture
Manoeuvring	0.2304	0.2880	3.362	0.3362	0.216	0.288	on/off-joint impact

Fig.13: Maximum Dent (side view) in LS-DYNA

Fig.14: Maximum dent (Front view) in LS-DYNA

The deformation and Stresses (for normal conditions at HWL) at Jacket Leg due to collision away from the joint(off-joint) have been provided by the graphs below:

The deformation and Stresses (for extreme conditions at HWL) at Jacket Leg due to collision on a point away from the joint(off-joint) have been provided by the graphs below:

The deformation and Stresses (for normal conditions at HWL) at Jacket Leg due to collision on a joint (on-joint) have been provided by the graphs below:

The deformation and Stresses (for extreme conditions at HWL) at Jacket Leg due to collision on a joint from the joint(on-joint) have been provided by the graphs below:

Relative Error Computation

Table 15: Relative Error Computation for results validation

Impact Scenario	Source of Data	Deformation (m)	Stress (10 ⁵ kN/m ²)	Relative Error from Excel (Deformation)	Relative Error from Excel (Stress)
Side	Reference	0.2352	2.27		
	This work	0.2253	2.00	0.0421	0.1189
Bow	Reference	0.2724	2.93		
	This work	0.2623	2.61	0.0371	0.1226
Manoeuvring	Reference	0.3224	3.06		
	This work	0.3113	2.83	0.0334	0.075

Fig.14: Deformation-Time Graph

Fig.15: Stress-Time Graph

Fig.16: Deformation from Reference work^[5]

Fig.17: Deformation from this research

Conclusion

After studying the global and local response to the jacket structure, specifically to the leg, the following conclusions are deduced:

- Deformation or dent depth on the jacket leg due to impact is observed to be elliptical according to this research which confirmed the observation made by Sumiwi and Afrizal (2014), in their research
- The average deformation is 0.28335m which exceeds the installed jacket leg thickness of 0.216m by 31.181% but falls below the minimum required leg thickness by 23.394%
- A minimum of 0.288m Jacket leg thickness should be adopted for Jackets in the Natuna sea to avoid fracture in the incidence of collision.

- Dent depth and stress values at joints impact were 21.429% and 28.205% respectively lesser than that of the off-joint due to the presence of braces.
- Bracing strength plays a vital role in the deformation procession during the collision and tends to reduce the dent depth appreciably
- To minimize collisions of Service vessels and Jacket platforms on the Natuna Sea, Stakeholders and policy formulators need to establish safety zones around platforms
- The prediction of the dent depth in mm (y) at a time in s (x) during collision is given by the polynomial equation:
 - Sideways: $y=14.20x^3-14.42x^2+4.60x-0.23$
 - Maneuvering: $y=167.32x^3-126.02x^2+30.91x-2.15$
 - Head-on: $y=2.46x^3-2.34x^2+0.69x+0.20$

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